

A Study on the Impact of Social Media Marketing on Consumer Behavior

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ABSTRACT

The fastest and developed, adoption of social media on consumer behavior provides different new things of new marketing on a new product. Today's the internet, social media has been taken the status of high growth of every firm growth and these technology changes ways of doing business in their business world. Social media marketing for every organization, firms can adopt their own technology to advertising their products. In this research, we can assess the impact of social media marketing on consumer behavior towards buying a product or marketing a decision to buy a new product. While social media marketing also assess the impact a promotion marketing and door to door marketing. In this study totally 250 questionnaires were distributed among the colleges students and got back responses from 200 questionnaire only. The research used convenient simple random sampling method. Researcher were used statistical tools such as **Multiple regression analysis, ANOVA, Chi-Square test, and Simple Percentage Analysis** and interpret the analysis finally results shows that the positive impact on the social media marketing on consumer behavior.

KEYWORDS: Social media marketing, promotional marketing, consumer behavior

INTRODUCTION

Shopping on social networking can come in various names, for example, web shopping, web purchasing and Internet shopping, all allude to the same method of acquiring or purchasing items through Internet utilizing Social Media and distinctive web shopping sites, Online networking (SM) are electronic administrations which are otherwise called "Long range informal communication Sites" allude to network of connections and associations among disparate clients (gatherings or individuals). By the start of 21st century, the use of internet and social media has become a part of business strategies. Social media marketing is the modern tool for marketing in 21st century (Nanji, 2015). Almost many firms using social media marketing as the use of social media increased. With the revolution of internet/IT, the way of doing business has changed and it's necessary to firm to adopt the new technology. So, nowadays firms are using internet/IT to market their product and these tools used by researchers, practitioners and policy makers. The most important body of academic work on this topic is the applied psychology and consumer behavior literature which has discussed ways in which the content of marketing communication engages consumers and captures attention. However, most of this work has tested and refined theories about content primarily in laboratory settings.

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Review of literature

As Hesseet al. (2009) said that now consumers are expecting to gain 24-hour access to information by online applications and many other digital ways, they are also expecting 24-hour customer service as well as self-serve options through online sources. Now consumers want to leave the traditional system for getting information and want to utilize latest technology.

As Chi 2011, said that social media marketing described as a "connection between brands and consumers, while social media marketing is providing a way to consumers for social interaction and centered networking." Social media has gained the position as a primary source for choosing a product by the consumers (Cocktail Analysis, 2012; Fleishman-Hillard, 2012).

Armstrong and Kotler, 2011 said that the rapid development in the social media application has gained overwhelming majority in the Marketing practices. Companies market performance and the products of the companies influenced by the huge quantity of data and information which are generated by users on internet.

Chen, 2014 The quality of product also influences consumer's perception. The consumer will pay the price if its quality is good (AmalPramanic, regional business director

Oral-B). Packaging is also direct links with the consumer perception. A product with outstanding packaging design also draws the attention of the consumer (Deepak Manchandra, manager packaging development, Dabur). Concluding current literature, it can deduced that whatever the marketing method is one should keep in mind these factors which influences consumer perception.

Bird, 2000. The main objective of direct marketing is to increase their customers (Baier, 2003). Many professionals says that direct marketing is more capable way to attain the marketing goals, gathering, examining and using information about actual and potential customers. One of the most current definition of direct marketing is “direct marketing is attractive system that a company use to measurable response and to achieve the deal in any position”

Statement of the problem

In recent years social media marketing has emerged as a new marketing tool. The aim of the organizations is to enhance the profitability by using the effective marketing strategies. Furthermore the main focus of every firm is to maximize the profitability and reduction of cost of production. Every firm use different social media for marketing like such as Facebook, twitter and other media. Internet is in the access of almost every person who is using a mobile phone as the introduction of 3G/4G/ services. So, this rapid growth of internet is a signal towards using internet as a marketing tool and its nice opportunity for any firm to change the consumer behavior through social media marketing.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analysis the socio economic profile of the respondents
2. To find out the relationship between Social Media Marketing and consumer behavior
3. To examine the impact of social media marketing on consumer behavior

Hypothesis

- H1** : Social Media Marketing has significant impact on Consumer Behavior.
- H2** : Promotional Marketing has positive impact on Consumer Behavior
- H3** : Direct Marketing has positive impact on Consumer Behavior

PROPOSAL MODEL

Research Methodology:

Research can be defined as “A scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic.” Research methods or techniques, thus refer to the methods the researchers use in performing research operations.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size is such a way that equal number of samples should be distributed among the private colleges’ students only. Such that simple random sampling method is used to determine the size of the sample size is 200 has been circulated with equal number of questionnaire.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

The researcher used both primary data and secondary data to this research.

RESEARCH TOOL

A structured, closed end questionnaire was designed and used for the study. It consists of 20 multiple- choice questions.

STATIATICAL TOOLS USED

- Simple Percentage analyzed.
- ANOVA
- Chi- Square Test
- Multiple Regression

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- Only limited number of studies was available as reference material.
- For the study the buying behavior of consumer behavior through social media marketing.
- For the study population is considered without indifference for the nature of their work.
- Consumer behavior, buying perception is a critical area was reluctant to share the information.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Demographic profile of the respondents

S. No	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Gender: Male	127	62.5
	Female	73	37.5
2.	Age 21-25 years	141	97.2
	26-30 years	59	02.8
3.	Qualification: UG	80	0.4
	PG	85	0.425
	Others	35	0.175

Source Primary data

Interpretation;

From the above table shows that the gender of the respondents male are (125) 62.5% and female (73) 37.5% and Age of the respondents were 21-25 years old (141) 97.2% and 26-30 years of the respondents were (59) 0.2.8% finally educational qualification of the respondents were UG,PG,and Others respectively (80,85,35) 0.4%,0.425% and 0.175%.

MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

S. No.	Factors	Consumer behavior
1	Social media marketing	.180*
2	Promotional marketing	.156*
3	Direct Marketing	.680*

R.Suqare .765
 Adj.R.Square .342
 Standard Error` 1.675

Regression equation

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + E \quad (1)$$

Consumer Behavior = 1016 + .180(Social media marketing) + .156(Promotional marketing) + .680(Direct Marketing) + E

INTERPRETATION

The result of this regression shows the effect of Social media marketing, Promotional Marketing, Direct marketing and consumer behavior among the college Students in Coimbatore city (N=200). To see the factors which influence consumer behavior, multiple linear Regressions were implied and see that social media marketing is influencing on consumer behavior. Predictor of research was Social Media Marketing, Promotional Marketing and direct Marketing. The results indicated a significant regression model where $p < .001$ and model summary explained that 40% variation by the predictors on measuring variable. Independent Variables that have shown statistically significant relation with Consumer behavior were: Social Media Marketing ($p < .01$), Promotional Marketing ($p < .01$) and Direct Marketing ($p < .05$).

FINDINGS, SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION**Major findings**

Consumer behavior is the indicator that establish link between the consumer's interest and actual purchase of the consumer. This study identifies and incorporates various marketing tolls which influence the consumer behavior.

- Gender of the respondents male are (125) 62.5% and female (73) 37.5% and Age of the respondents were 21-25 years old (141) 97.2% and 26-30 years of the respondents were (59) 0.2.8% finally educational qualification of the respondents were UG,PG, and Others respectively (80,85,35) 0.4%,0.425% and 0.175%.
- Consumer Behavior = 1016 + .180 (Social media marketing) + .156 (Promotional marketing) + .680(Direct Marketing)
- Although the promotional and door to door marketing influence more than social media but the positive results of social media also show that it will become more influential in coming days because it is more helpful and advance technique of marketing for any organization to promote and give brand awareness to the customers.
- brand awareness companies should create groups and home pages on social media in order to target consumers and can easily influence consumer perception regarding to their products.

Suggestions

- Being active on social media helps to influence more consumer perception because thing which are new, distinctive and innovative are consider more by people.
- Social media in-built tools such as sending messages and regular newsletters to users containing the newest information regarding new products helps to promote and give awareness to consumer about new launched product.
- Consumer's needs should be easily satisfied by companies by communicating and listening to them, Providing care and services such as solving problems, taking suggestions, feedbacks and answering queries are effective ways to enhance the relationship between consumers and companies on social media.
- Social media marketing companies easily attract more consumers specially those real contributors and

engaging them into discussions which helps to bring more innovation in products according to consumer demands.

- Social media marketing also helps in the long term as consumer establish more and more trust and perceived value and when consumers have needs, the companies has high likelihood of a consumer to purchase a product.

Conclusion

This research has impact on consumer perception. In table beta value of social media marketing is 0.180 this shows that there is weak but positive relationship between social media marketing and consumer perception. Promotional marketing beta value is 0.156 which also show that there is weak relationship between promotional marketing and consumer perception. Direct marketing beta value is 0.680 which show that there is moderate relationship between direct marketing and consumer behavior. So direct marketing and selling has greatest beta value this variable has more impact on consumer behavior rather than social media and promotional tools. Results show that the hypothesis is accepted.

Future Direction

The nature of the study is exploratory, in this research data is surveyed only from student. It may be possible that people from different fields have different response. It may analyze data from different fields. It may also possible preferences of people from one region or country to other region or country may different towards using of social media and buying online product after seeing advertisement on social media.

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Website

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